

ABOUT THE ETHNO-ECOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE REGIONS

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ABSTRACT

The influence of ethno-ecological zones based on altitudes, which are also mentioned in the article, can be observed in the formation of settlements in the Fergana Valley. It is noted that the development began in the upper, third and fourth ethno-ecological regions of the valley by the population engaged in animal husbandry, horticulture, handicrafts and lalmikor farming.

Keywords: livestock, horticulture, handicrafts, lalmikor farming, regional center, hills, desert.

INTRODUCTION

In the territorial location of settlements, the development of the earth's surface by humans is a very long historical process, which is directly related to the development of the territory. Therefore, the influence of ethno-ecological regions based on the above-mentioned elevations can be observed in the formation of settlements in the Fergana Valley. It is noted in the literature that the assimilation was initially initiated by the population engaged in animal husbandry, horticulture, handicrafts, and lalmikor farming in the upper, third and fourth, ethno-ecological regions of the valley.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The oldest Chinese written sources state that there were 70 "cities" in Fergana, inhabited by 60,000 families or 300,000 people [5].

Most of these cities can also be seen in the fourth, third ethnoecological zone above the Fergana Valley. In the settlements of these regions, the population was mainly engaged in animal husbandry, arable farming and mountain gardening. After

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the semi-sedentary life of the cattle-breeding population began to be observed, it was observed that they descended to the lower parts of the valley and prepared a special place for themselves for the winter. In such settlements the settlements are formed in the form of fortifications. We see that the word 'fortress' is also more present in their names. While such "fortresses" are in the form of crowded, commercial, and handicraft villages in the winter months, in other months the bulk of the population has migrated to mountain pastures. In our toponymic research in the region of the Fergana Valley, where mountain, hill and desert landscapes meet, more than 100 place names with the words "fortress" and "fortress" were recorded. These fort-shaped settlements are more typical of semi-settled Kyrgyz, Kipchak, Turkish, and Karakalpak cattle-breeding populations, and are usually built near Uzbek- and Tajik-farming villages. It was pointed out by S.S. Gubaeva that most of these names were named after the seed or seed elder who constituted it. In our initial research, it was possible to identify ethnonyms such as Nogaykurgan, Kipchakkurgan, Kyrgyzkurgan, Kazakkurgan, anthroponyms such as Turakurgan, Khankurgan, Khojakurgan, Yusufkurgan, Sofikurgan. Also, in this region of the Fergana valley, the toponyms Kyzylkurgan, Ortakurgan, Kazykurgan are 2 times, Karakurgan, Tepakurgan toponyms are 3 times, Uchkurgan, Tashkurgan toponyms are 4 times, Yangikurgan is 12 times [1, 2, 3].

RESULTS AND THEIR DISCUSSION

From an ecological point of view, the ethno-ecological law put forward by L.N. Humilev. The settlements formed during the period under study began to form at the confluence of hills, mountains and desert landscapes. Examples of such settlements are Kasan, Chodak, Aksi, Osh, Aravan, Ershi, Kuva, Uzgen, Pop. The normalization of the amount of anthropogenic pressure on nature with increasing population in settlements with such different landscape zones is taken into account. In these areas, the fertility of pastures, "forest-gardens" used in mountain gardening, and arable lands has been reduced and prevented from degradation. Nomadic, semi-nomadic and sedentary

settlements based on the use of each landscape zone in accordance with its "nature" [2].

Economic relations in these settlements are vertical, and in the ethno-ecological regions of the Fergana Valley, corresponding to the above-mentioned elevations, these relations have been preserved until the development of irrigated agriculture in the valley. As a result, in the fourth region, settlements such as Voruh, Isfara, Botkent, Shohimardon, Sokh, Novqat, Osh, Chodak, Chorkesar, Sefedbulon became interconnected, and these settlements served as "regional centers" in ethno-landscape regions. At the same time, the functions of these settlements with the formation of irrigated farming culture in the valley, that is, in addition to the function of the regional center, are also assigned the function of "sacred shrines". [4].

In contrast to this region, more development of handicrafts and trade, horticulture was observed in the settlements that occurred in the third region. As an example, we can study the settlements of Rishtan, Isfara. Formed between the Adir and desert landscapes, the development of handicrafts (Rishtan pottery) and horticulture (cultivation of Isfara apricots) together with the nomadic population allowed to increase the population without burdening the natural landscape. Therefore, these centers developed faster than other surrounding settlements. In addition, we can see that in each of the settlements of Yaypan, Arsif, Kuva, Mingtepa, Aravan, Kasan, Yangikurgan, Chartak, Olmos, Pop, Chust, in addition to animal husbandry and agriculture, developed a profession based on the use of certain specialized natural resources. Viticulture and winemaking in Yaypan, walnut growing in Arsif, pomegranate growing in Quva, tandoori growing in Mingtepa and Aravan, horse breeding, pottery in Kasan, gaynali and koksulton in Yangikurgan, pistachio and almond growing in Chartak, blacksmithing in Chust, apple growing in Damascus developed, refined, and accumulated, traditions, skills, and competencies have been passed down from generation to generation.

As in other arid regions, the development of the irrigation system in the Fergana Valley has also affected the location of key settlements.

By the end of the 19th century, the current situation in the settlement of settlements in the Fergana Valley was fully formed. In addition to the irrigation factor, of course, natural, economic and social factors also influenced this location. Despite the small size of the Fergana Valley, under the influence of the above factors, the following ecologically significant features can be observed in the location of settlements (villages).

First, on the right bank of the Syrdarya, settlements are located in river valleys in a long, narrow, striped position. The ribbon-like location of the villages in the valley of the rivers Podshootasay, Chartaksay, Chodaksay, Govasay, Kosonsoy in Namangan district can be seen from the geographical map developed in the late XIX century.

An ecologically important aspect of such a location is the horizontal arrangement of connections between settlements. The essence of ethno-ecological culture of this period can be understood by using the phrase "drinking water from a ditch" left over from the ancient Turks. The principle of a basin-specific approach to geography has helped to ensure environmental and social justice in relations. In such areas, the recommendations concerning the reconciliation of water users living in the upper and lower reaches of a river or stream in Hidoya's work were extremely pertinent and useful.

Second, all the rivers in the valley formed conical distributions after passing through the hilly region of the region. First of all, the Sox conical distribution can be cited as a typical example of distributions. In addition, at the exits of the hills of the rivers Isfara, Shohimardonsoy, Isfayramsay, Aravonsay, Akbura, Moylisay, Norin, the settlements are located in conical distributions on the basis of the above legislation.

It is worthwhile to study the location of these settlements from a socio-ecological point of view is that the distances between them and the adequacy of irrigated land, which is the main means of production, have been ensured.

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Third, as a result of the formation of trade and cultural ties in the villages located on a flat surface in the conical spreads, the "central habitat" of each spread is formed. The third type of settlements can be seen in the middle of the conical spreads, in the lower part of the irrigation network, relative to the "central settlement". Such centers as Isfara, Kokand, Altiyarik, Margilan, Asaka, Andijan, Uchkurgan. Typically, the central location is located in the middle of the conical distribution, which has led to its enlargement under the influence of economic factors (shopping center, education, health, management, transport hub). An example of this type of settlement is the location of the city of Margilan and surrounding villages.

Fourth, the formation of large isolated villages in the desert landscapes of Central Fergana. Such settlements as Boz, Yazyovan, Mingbulak still serve as district centers.

CONCLUSION

Although villages that do not specialize in agriculture are rare in the valley, mixed-duty species are common. The villages in the upper reaches of the rivers, starting from the mountains around the Fergana Valley, serve as "sacred shrines" (ethno-ecological approaches). The names of the saints and prophets belonging to Islam make up the majority of the toponyms of these villages. In the second group of villages, which do not specialize in agriculture, the words bazaar and caravan are often used. The inhabitants of such villages are more engaged in trade.

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